

Rotating parking improvement analysis applying payback

*Análise de Melhoria em Estacionamento Rotativo Aplicando
Payback*
*Análisis de mejora del aparcamiento rotativo aplicando la
recuperación de la inversión*

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Abstract: Based on the need to obtain an adequate way to make decisions in strategic management generating a competitive advantage, we show the main planning tools that allow you to analyze investment and financial return. By investing today to satisfy the need to better supply what you have been looking for, quality of parking service and user experience, to increase profitability and competitiveness. As a methodology, a case study will be used in the JBD Rotating Parking, located in the center of Santa Barbara do Oeste, addressing a survey of fundamental information and justifications, through an analysis of the market scenario in relation to the provision of services over time by the parking lot and in the midst of seeking its investment opportunities to develop a coverage model for the vehicles, so that it is possible to obtain a better cost and a better financial return meeting our expectations.

Keywords: *Parking; Costs; Return; Analysis; Payback.*

Resumo: Com base na necessidade de se obter uma forma adequada para a tomada de decisões na gestão estratégica gerando uma vantagem competitiva, mostramos as principais ferramentas de planejamento que permite analisar investimento e retorno financeiro. Ao investir hoje para satisfazer a necessidade de melhor suprir o que tem procurado, qualidade do serviço de estacionamento e da experiência do usuário, de forma a aumentar a lucratividade e a competitividade. Como metodologia, será utilizado um estudo de caso no Estacionamento rotativo JBD, localizado no centro de Santa Barbara do Oeste, abordando um levantamento de informações e justificativas fundamentais, por meio de uma análise do cenário de mercado em relação a prestação de serviços ao longo do tempo pelo estacionamento e em meio a buscar suas oportunidades de investimento para elaboração de um modelo de cobertura para os veículos, de modo que seja possível obter um melhor custo e um melhor retorno financeiro atendendo nossas expectativas.

Palavras-chave: Estacionamento; Custos; Retorno; Análise; Payback.

Resumen: A partir de la necesidad de obtener una forma adecuada de tomar decisiones en la gestión estratégica generando una ventaja competitiva, mostramos las principales herramientas de planificación que permiten analizar la inversión y el retorno financiero. Invirtiendo hoy para satisfacer la necesidad de ofrecer de mejor manera lo que ha estado buscando, calidad del servicio de estacionamiento y experiencia de usuario, con el fin de aumentar la rentabilidad y la competitividad. Como metodología, se utilizará un estudio de caso en el Estacionamiento Rotativo JBD, ubicado en el centro de Santa Bárbara do Oeste, abordando un relevamiento de información fundamental y justificaciones, a través de un análisis del escenario del mercado en relación a la prestación de servicios a lo largo del tiempo por parte del estacionamiento y en medio de la búsqueda de sus oportunidades de inversión para desarrollar un modelo de cobertura para los vehículos, de manera que sea posible

obtener un mejor costo y un mejor retorno financiero cumpliendo con nuestras expectativas.

Palabras clave: *Estacionamiento; Costos; Devolución; Análisis; Amortización.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The JBD rotating parking lot in question is a vehicle movement location in the center of Santa Barbara Do Oeste. It serves various users, including residents, workers, customers of nearby establishments, and visitors.

A roof will be installed in the parking lot in early 2024, aiming to improve the user experience, protect parked vehicles from weather conditions, and potentially increase operational efficiency.

Investment analysis will be considered to decide the details of the development of this project, which is the process of evaluating and selecting projects, assets, or business opportunities to determine their financial viability and ability to generate a return on investment. It is vital in decision-making in all business spheres, from individual companies to governments and non-profit organizations. Investment analysis helps to allocate limited resources efficiently, minimizing risks and maximizing returns.

1.1 Problematization

"How can we optimize the management of a rotating parking lot in an urban area, considering the challenges of competition and growing demand for parking spaces?"

This problematization addresses a common scenario in cities, where rotating parking lots are essential in urban regions.

Therefore, the expression of parking policies can be defined as a set of measures and actions related to parking (management, redistribution, construction, etc.) that aim to balance the supply and demand of spaces by increasing or reducing them. According to Dal Sasso Meira (2009, p. 43), the following aspects of the market must be analyzed:

- a) Demand Management: How can parking spaces be balanced during peak and off-peak periods? What strategies can be implemented to manage demand equitably?
- b) Costs and Revenues: How do you develop the operational costs of a rotating parking lot, such as maintenance and personnel, while generating revenues to cover these costs and possibly generate profit?
- c) Public Acceptance: How can we involve the community and stakeholders in decision-making related to rotating parking, ensuring that everyone's interests are considered?

Highlights The complexity involved in managing urban parking lots and the importance of parking in transportation policies have often been underestimated. However, the fact is that cars are typically parked 95% of the time in their lives. This means that the search for a parking space is, in potential terms, more problematic than any other concern that one might have regarding the lack of space to accommodate them when they are in motion (PALMER; FERRIS, 2010, p. 22).

Consider operational efficiency and environmental, social, and economic impacts. Finding solutions to these challenges can contribute to a more efficient and affordable quality of life for civilians.

1.2 Objectives

"The objective of this project is to implement a roof in the existing JBD rotating parking lot, which is around 12.00m x 36.00m and has been located for three years in the center of Santa Barbara do Oeste, aiming to provide greater convenience and comfort to users in order to offer a condition to protect vehicles against adverse weather conditions."

The objective highlights the need for a roof in a rotating parking lot and sets out several specific goals that can be achieved,

Based on the objectives of offering protection to parking users' vehicles, specific conditions are increasingly evident, as can be seen in the references of France (2013), Carvalho et al. (2013), and COST– *Technical Committee on Transport* (2005):

- a) Improved User Experience: Covering provides users a more pleasant experience when parking and returning to their vehicles, creating a more friendly and welcoming environment. This can contribute to customer satisfaction and increase the attractiveness of the parking lot. Paid parking with progressive hourly pricing is a dissuasive nature for residents (who will have to look for off-street parking) and commuters (who will have to turn to other modes of transport or use private parking). On the other hand, it is inviting for visitors, who will find it easier to find a short-term paid parking space. The city center will be more attractive. (FRANCE, 2013, p. 30).
- b) Increase Operational Efficiency: Reduce the time users spend searching for parking spaces and entering/exiting the parking lot due to weather conditions, thus improving the turnover of spaces. An alternative basis for taxation would be the parking spaces of properties or enterprises, even if private. (CARVALHO et al., 2013, p. 20)
- c) Safety and Security: Covering can contribute to the safety of users by providing appropriate lighting and reducing the risk of accidents, robberies, and vandalism. In addition, it protects vehicles from the direct effects of the weather, which can prevent damage and breakdowns. " Successful decision-making processes in parking measures are complex and influenced by many external factors. Under normal conditions, deciding where to go and how to get there is only partially rational. It is only under the influence of impactful external circumstances (such as parking restrictions) that people can reconsider their travel options on a more rational basis. This can lead to adjustments in their transport patterns (times, destinations, modal options, parking locations, etc.)" (*COST Technical Committee on Transport*, 2005, p. 89, our translation).

Parking should not be confused with short-term parking. Retailers highly appreciate the possibility of stopping for a quick purchase, which they see as a

way of capturing passing customers. A high turnover of parking spaces leads to optimizing the number of visitors. Faure (2011) provides clear direction for implementing the roof project, ensuring that it meets users' needs and environmental, aesthetic, and regulatory standards and is financially viable. The roof will improve the quality of the parking service and the user experience.

2. JUSTIFICATION

The decision to install a roof over a rotating parking lot is a choice that requires solid justification, considering several factors that affect both users and the parking lot operation. Below are some fundamental justifications raised through an analysis of the market scenario concerning the provision of services over time by the parking lot and while seeking its opportunities among the strengths that may become references over time:

- a) Vehicle protection: Prolonged exposure to adverse weather conditions can damage vehicles, such as paint fading, hail damage, or internal damage due to sun exposure. Covering helps protect parked vehicles from these risks, increasing credibility and making potential retail customers comfortable about parking monthly.
- b) Increased Parking Turnover With the protection offered by the cover, users can move more quickly in and out of the parking lot, which increases parking turnover. This is especially beneficial for a rotating parking lot where entry and exit speed is essential, expanding its service capacity.
- c) Create a safer and more comfortable environment for users, minimizing the risk of slipping on wet floors and mud in puddles and reducing exposure to extreme temperatures.
- d) Property Value: A roof over a parking garage can increase the property's value or positively impact adjacent properties, making it more attractive to investors and renters.

These justifications demonstrate that installing a roof over a parking lot significantly benefits users, operators, and the urban environment. It is essential to carefully analyze the costs and benefits before considering the specific needs of the parking lot and the community in which it is located.

2.1 Methodology

Our study will be a case study because it consists of determining an object of study, selecting variables that could influence it, defining the forms of control, and observing the effects that the variable produces, which include the following steps (BRYMAN, 1995). The case study followed a methodology, therefore, Experimental Research, because in addition to being suitable for the case in question, the experiment represents the best example of scientific research.

Data related to parking operations were available, such as occupancy rates, average length of stay, revenue, operating costs, climate records, feedback from users who frequent the parking lot, and reasons for not using it. Thus, the cost

and benefit analysis of installing the cover was conducted through a *payback analysis—period* (Return Period).

2.2 Investment Analysis Methods

Regarding the organization's performance, another point considered in the analysis is the use of investment techniques, which are used so that the organization chooses more profitable alternatives. For this, it is necessary to observe some variables that influence the business system and bring the desired profitability (HUMMEL ETASCHNER, 1995). The most common ones are:

1. Net Present Value (NPV): The net present value criterion is the classic model for investment decisions and comprises the following variables (PADOVEZ, 2005, p. 107)
2. Internal Rate of Return (IRR): The *Internal Rate of Return* (IRR) is one of the most sophisticated ways of evaluating capital investment proposals. It represents the discount rate that equals cash inflows with cash outflows at a single point in time. In other words, the rate produces an NPV equal to zero. (KASSAI et al., 2007)
3. *Payback Period* (Payback Period): The payback period is the time required for an investment to generate sufficient cash flows to recover the initial investment. *It* refers to the time required for the company to recover the initial investment in a project through cash flow inflows and is used to aid decision-making for projects with similar performance (DAMODARAM, 2002; GITMAN, 2010).

3. RISKS IN INVESTMENT ANALYSIS

Overestimation or underestimation of future cash flows can lead to the acceptance of a project that should be rejected or the rejection of a project that should be accepted. Furthermore, the NPV (Net Present Value) method assumes that the discount rate is the same throughout the project. (GROPPELLI; NIKBAKHT, 2005, p.138):

1. Market Risk: Economic changes, currency fluctuations, and changes in asset prices may affect investment performance.
2. Financial Risk: Issues such as leverage and debt can increase an investment's vulnerability to changes in financial conditions.
3. Operational Risk: Internal problems, such as management failures, production problems, or competition, can negatively impact investment results.
4. Regulatory and Legal Risk: Changes in regulation or litigation can have significant financial implications.

In a broader view, Galesne (1999) reports that the uncertainty of future entries and revenue is proportional to how new or unknown the product is.

3.1 Case Study

payback analysis regarding the case study of the coverage implementation in the rotating parking lot. The strategic decision to improve the parking infrastructure represents a significant milestone in the continuous search for improvements.

Next, the simple and discounted *payback analysis* plays a crucial role in assessing the project's financial viability, providing the period required to recover the initial investment. In this specific context, we examine in detail the costs associated with the implementation of the roof, considering factors such as materials, labor, and maintenance, for a total of R\$45,000.00 required for the improvement.

3.2 Simple Payback

The simple *payback period*, the capital recovery period, is formed by the sum of the negative cash flow values with the positive cash flow values until this sum results in zero. A project with a *payback* lower than another indicates a lower risk (KASSAI et al., 2007). This is the time required for the company to recover its initial investment in a project, calculated with its cash inflows. Based on the payback period, an investment is accepted if its calculated period is less than a predetermined number of years.

For the feasibility of the parking lot coverage, the values in Table 1 were obtained as the central reference budget. The investment value will be R\$ 45,000.00. The other cash flow values represent an average of the monthly values of the last three years of the parking lot's existence, totaling an average annual revenue expected for the next few years.

Table 1: Cash Flow from Implementation Covered by Simple Payback

Years	Cash flow	Balance	Return
0	- 45,000.00	- 45,000.00	
1	30,000.00	- 15,000.00	30,000.00
2	32,000.00	17,000.00	15,000.00
3	30,000.00	47,000.00	
4	34,000.00	81,000.00	
5	35,000.00	116,000.00	
		Total	45,000.00

Source: Own elaboration.

$$\text{payback} = \frac{15,000.00}{32,000.00} \text{ months}$$

$$\text{payback} = 0.46875 \text{ Months}$$

Calculating the total months:

0.46875	x	12	=	5.6
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$$\text{payback} = 1 \text{ year and } 6 \text{ months}$$

Calculating the return on investment using simple *Payback*, the amount obtained after the first year of R\$30,000.00 will result in a difference of R\$15,000.00 to be

received for the next year, resulting in a cash inflow of R\$32,000.00. In this case, the proportional amount missing to make up the total investment on the cash inflow amount must be calculated.

To calculate the fraction of 0.46875 of a year, you must multiply this value by the number of months in a year. This way, you can see that the return on investment will be possible after approximately one year and six months.

4. PAYBACK DISCOUNTED

This method was designed to correct one of the main flaws of *payback*, which is disregarding the time value of money.

In discounted *payback*, an investment is acceptable when the return of the invested capital occurs in a time equal to or less than the company's standard.

(LEMES JR et al. 2010).

To explicitly take into account the differences in terms of dates of occurrence of cash flows when using the *payback method*, the condition of the value of money over time must be highlighted and, thus, have the most realistic view possible of the returns on investments, by calculating the present value of cash inflows at the appropriate discount rate, and then determining the payback period *with* the present value of the inflows (GITIMAM, 2005, p. 340).

Table 2: Cash Flow from Implementation Covered by Discounted Payback

Year	Discount rate	12%	Balance	Return
	Cash flow	Cash Flow		
0	- 45,000.00	Discounted	- 45,000.00	
1	30,000.00	26,726.06	- 18,273.94	26,726.06
2	32,000.00	28,507.80	10,233.85	18,273.94
3	30,000.00	26,726.06	36,959.91	
4	34,000.00	30,289.53	67,249.44	
5	35,000.00	31,180.40	98,429.84	
			TOTAL	45,000.00

Source: Own elaboration.

$$\text{Payback} = 1 \text{ year and } \frac{18,273.94}{28,507.80} \text{ months}$$

$$\text{Payback} = 1 \text{ year and } 0.6410156 \text{ months}$$

Calculating the total months:

0.641016	x	12	=	7.6921875	months
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Return by Discounted *Payback* will be after one year and eight months.

For discounted *payback*, subtract the discounted cash flow value for each year from the initial investment at 12.25%.

Using the Selic rate as the discount rate, the introductory interest rate of the country's economy, is applied in the *payback* concerning the interest paid in bank loans. Defined at the last meeting held on 11/01/2023, Copom (Monetary Policy Committee) decided to set the Selic rate at 12.25% per year (BULHÕE, 2023)

For the feasibility of the parking lot coverage, the values in Table 2 were obtained as the central reference budget. In the first year, the already discounted cash flow is 26,726.06 with the difference of 18,273.93 for the next year, being divided by the discounted working capital entry of 28,507.80 from the second year, to then total a total of 7.6921875 months, that is, there will be a return on the amount invested after approximately one year and eight months, making the project viable since the invested capital will be available for future new investments and possible cash needs after one year and eight months.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on investment analysis, an essential tool for making informed financial decisions, we conclude that installing a JBD parking cover is an advantageous measure that benefits users, operational efficiency, and the environment.

In addition to obtaining a viable projection of the return on investment, it is also expected that current parking customers will keep their cars in the parking facilities, contributing to the amount of their monthly and annual revenue within the calculated average values. However, greater demand from other users is also expected, thus increasing revenue to optimize the return on investment so that it is possible to have a return on investment value even lower than one year and eight months.

Installing the roof on behalf of JBD Car Park is a positive example of how improving user experience, operational efficiency, and sustainability can result in solid financial benefits. This project is a testament to the car park's commitment to providing high-quality service and promoting responsible practices.

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